

CONTRIBUTION TO THE KNOWLEDGE OF THE GENUS *OTIORHYNCHUS* (COLEOPTERA, CURCULIONIDAE) OF UKRAINE. PART 1

I. V. Kizub¹ & A. I. Slutsky²

¹Ukrainian Entomological Society;
New York Medical College, 15 Dana Road,
Valhalla, 10595, New York, USA.

E-mails: buzzmann@ukr.net; igor.kizub@gmail.com; ikizub_p@nymc.edu.

²Ukrainian Entomological Society,
Kharkiv, Ukraine.

E-mail: alslutsky@gmail.com.

Kizub, I. V. & Slutsky, A. I. Contribution to the knowledge of the genus *Otiorynchus* (Coleoptera, Curculionidae) of Ukraine. Part 1. Summary. New records of the genus *Otiorynchus* Germar, 1822 species (Coleoptera, Curculionidae, Etiminae) in Ukraine is represented: *O. albidus* Stierlin, 1861; *O. asphaltinus* Germar, 1824; *O. atronitens* Formánek, 1925; *O. aurosparsus* Germar, 1824; *O. balcanicus* Stierlin, 1861; *O. brauneri* Smirnov, 1912; *O. brunneus* Gyllenhal, 1834; *O. fullo* (Schrank, 1781); *O. ligustici* (Linnaeus, 1758); *O. ovalipennis* Boheman, 1842; *O. ovatus ovatus* (Linnaeus, 1758); *O. pilosus pilosus* Gyllenhal, 1834; *O. pseudomias* Hochhuth, 1847; *O. raucus* (Fabricius, 1777); *O. tristis* (Scopoli, 1763); *O. velutinus* Germar, 1824; *O. vitis theodosianus* Retowski, 1887. Updated information regarding geographical distribution of these species in Ukraine and the Palearctic Region is given. In the present paper we report new evidences of introducing *O. asphaltinus* into Kyiv Region. Also, we report northernmost record of *O. aurosparsus* in Ukraine and the first record of this species in Chernihiv Region of Ukraine. We recommend including this species in The Red Lists of Ukraine and The Red Lists of Chernihiv Region of Ukraine as a rare species on the border of its range.

Key words: Coleoptera, Curculionidae, Entiminae, *Otiorynchus*, Palearctic Region, Ukraine.

Кізуб І. В. та Слущкий О. І. До пізнання фауни роду *Otiorynchus* (Coleoptera, Curculionidae) України. Частина 1. Резюме. Надано інформацію про нові знахідки видів роду *Otiorynchus* Germar, 1822 (Coleoptera, Curculionidae, Etiminae) в Україні: *O. albidus* Stierlin, 1861; *O. asphaltinus* Germar, 1824; *O. atronitens* Formánek, 1925; *O. aurosparsus* Germar, 1824; *O. balcanicus* Stierlin, 1861; *O. brauneri* Smirnov, 1912; *O. brunneus* Gyllenhal, 1834; *O. fullo* (Schrank, 1781); *O. ligustici* (Linnaeus, 1758); *O. ovalipennis* Boheman, 1842; *O. ovatus ovatus* (Linnaeus, 1758); *O. pilosus pilosus* Gyllenhal, 1834; *O. pseudomias* Hochhuth, 1847; *O. raucus* (Fabricius, 1777); *O. tristis* (Scopoli, 1763); *O. velutinus* Germar, 1824; *O. vitis theodosianus* Retowski, 1887. Надано оновлену інформацію щодо географічного поширення цих видів в Україні та Палеарктичному регіоні. В даній статті ми надаємо нові свідчення щодо інтродукції *O. asphaltinus* до Київської області України. Також, ми сповіщаємо про найпівнічнішу знахідку *O. aurosparsus* в Україні та першу знахідку цього виду в Чернігівській області України. Ми рекомендуємо внести цей вид до Червоних списків України та Чернігівський області України, як рідкісний вид на межі свого ареалу.

Ключові слова: Coleoptera, Curculionidae, Entiminae, *Otiorynchus*, Палеарктичний регіон, Україна.

Кізуб И. В. и Слущкий А. И. К познанию фауны рода *Otiorynchus* (Coleoptera, Curculionidae) Украины. Часть 1. Резюме. Представлена информация о новых находках видов рода *Otiorynchus* Germar, 1822 (Coleoptera, Curculionidae, Etiminae) в Украине: *O. albidus* Stierlin, 1861; *O. asphaltinus* Germar, 1824; *O. atronitens* Formánek, 1925; *O. aurosparsus* Germar, 1824; *O. balcanicus* Stierlin, 1861; *O. brauneri* Smirnov, 1912; *O. brunneus* Gyllenhal, 1834; *O. fullo* (Schrank, 1781); *O. ligustici* (Linnaeus, 1758); *O. ovalipennis* Boheman, 1842; *O. ovatus ovatus* (Linnaeus, 1758); *O. pilosus pilosus* Gyllenhal, 1834; *O. pseudomias* Hochhuth, 1847; *O. raucus* (Fabricius, 1777); *O. tristis* (Scopoli, 1763); *O. velutinus* Germar, 1824; *O. vitis theodosianus* Retowski, 1887. Представлена обновленная информация о географическом распространении этих видов в Украине и Палеарктическом регионе. В данной статье мы представляем новые доказательства относительно интродукции *O. asphaltinus* в Киевскую область Украины. Так же, мы сообщаем о самой северной находке *O. aurosparsus* в Украине и первой находке этого вида в Черниговской области Украины. Мы рекомендуем внести этот вид в Красные списки Украины и Черниговской области Украины, как редкий вид на границе своего ареала.

Ключевые слова: Coleoptera, Curculionidae, Entiminae, *Otiorynchus*, Палеарктический регион, Украина.

Introduction

The genus *Otiorhynchus* is extremely rich in species and comprises over 1500 species distributed in the Palaearctic Region (Alonso-Zarazaga *et al.*, 2017). According to different sources, the Ukrainian fauna of the genus up to now comprises about 100 species (Alonso-Zarazaga *et al.*, 2017; Yunakov *et al.*, 2018 a) and has been reviewed in detail by Yunakov (2003 b) and recently by Yunakov and coauthors in a Survey of the weevils of Ukraine (Yunakov *et al.*, 2018 a). Additional important information regarding geographical distribution and biology of the genus *Otiorhynchus* in Ukraine has been given in other publications and databases (Yunakov, 1998; Mazur, 2002; Nazarenko & Sheshurak, 2003; Yunakov, 2003 a, b; Yunakov & Drogvalenko, 2013; Yunakov *et al.*, 2018 b). The present paper is a first in the proposed publication cycle addressed new faunistic information about the genus *Otiorhynchus* in Ukraine and the Palaearctic Region. This paper contains data on the new records and distribution of the genus species which range is mainly limited by southern and eastern regions of the country.

Material and methods

The study material is deposited in the I. V. Kizub private collection (Kyiv, Ukraine). The photographs were taken using the Nikon D90 camera with Sigma EX 150mm 1: 2.8 APO Macro DG HSM + Raynox DCR MacroScan Conversion lens. Nomenclature of taxa and synonymy for the species names are given according to The Cooperative Catalogue of Palaearctic Coleoptera Curculionoidea (CCPCC) (Alonso-Zarazaga *et al.*, 2017). Biogeographic division is given according to Rivas-Martínez *et al.* 2004.

Describing the range of *Otiorhynchus atronitens* Formánek, 1925, we use the term “orocrimean” (the prefix “oro-” means relating to mountains). In this term we follow Rivas-Martínez *et al.* 2004. as the name of the biogeographic sub-province of the Euxine province, which includes mountain part of the Crimea peninsula and part of the South Caucasus.

Results and discussion

Otiorhynchus (Choilisanus) balcanicus Stierlin, 1861 (Fig. 1)

Material examined. Crimea: Sevastopol, Kozacha Bay, 44.583501°N 33.415021°E, 06–19.07.2006, 12 ♀ (Kizub).

Distribution. Ukraine: the Crimea, Kherson, and Zaporizhia Regions, introduced in Kyiv Region (Yunakov, 2003 b; Yunakov *et al.*, 2018 a, b). Central, Southern,

and Eastern Europe, Southwestern Asia, Syria, and Iran (Alonso-Zarazaga *et al.*, 2017).

Biology. *Otiorhynchus balcanicus* is a nocturnal, parthenogenetic species inhabiting xerothermic and mixed nemoral forests on the plain and in the mountains (Yunakov, 2003 b; Yunakov *et al.*, 2018 a). Dendrobiotic and polyphagous species feeding on *Quercus pubescens*, *Q. robur*, *Betula borysthena*, and *Juniperus excelsa* (Yunakov *et al.*, 2018 a). The species could damage fruit trees in the south of Ukraine (Yunakov, 2003 b).

Otiorhynchus (Choilisanus) brunneus Gyllenhal, 1834

Material examined. Crimea: Sevastopol, National Preserve of Tauric Chersonesos, 44.61231°N 33.49185°E, 24.07.2004, 2 ♀ (Kizub); Sevastopol, Kozacha Bay, 44.583501°N 33.415021°E, 6–19.07.2006, 6 ♀ (Kizub); idem, 3–15.08.2008, 1 ♀ (Kizub); Kyiv Region: Sofiivska Borschagivka, 50.41424°N 30.36681°E, 10.04.2005, 1 ♀ (Kizub).

Distribution. Ukraine: the Crimea, Donetsk, Odesa, Kharkiv, Kherson, Kyiv, Mykolaiv, and Zaporizhia Regions (Yunakov *et al.*, 2018 a). Almost whole Europe, Southwestern Asia, Middle East, and Kyrgyzstan (Alonso-Zarazaga *et al.*, 2017).

Biology. Parthenogenetic, xerophilic species inhabiting steppes (Yunakov, 2003 b; Yunakov *et al.*, 2018 a). The species is a polyphagous and feeds on plants of the family Poaceae, *Potentilla* sp., and *Carduus* sp. (Yunakov *et al.*, 2018 a).

Taxonomic notes. *Otiorhynchus brunneus* by some authors is also regarded as belonging to the subgenus *Arammichnus* (Białooki & Germann, 2016).

Otiorhynchus (Choilisanus) pilosus pilosus Gyllenhal, 1834 (Fig. 2)

=caucasicus Stierlin, 1872

=querceti Arnoldi, 1965

Material examined. Crimea: Bakhchysarai District, between Vysoke and Sokolyne vill., 44.59409°N 33.94985°E, 25–27.04.2009, 1 ♀ (Khodakivska); Bakhchysarai District, Besh-Kosh Mt., 44.749444°N, 33.925556°E, 01.05.2010, 2 ♀ (Kizub).

Distribution. Ukraine: the Crimea, Donetsk, Kharkiv, and Luhansk Regions (Nazarenko & Sheshurak, 2003; Yunakov *et al.*, 2018 a, b). Moldova (Poiras, 2006), central and southern European part of Russia (Reitter, 1888; Isaev, 1998; Ismailova, 2007; Korotyaev, 2007; Korotyaev & Arzanov, 2010; Arzanov, 2012; Mukhtarova, 2012; Yunakov *et al.*, 2012; Korotyaev & Zabaluev, 2014; Arzanov, 2015; Mukhtarova & Abdurakhmanov, 2015; Krasnobaev, 2017; Brekhov, 2018), Ukraine (Nazarenko & Sheshurak, 2003; Yunakov, 2003 b; Yunakov *et al.*, 2018 a, b), Azerbaijan (Alonso-Zarazaga *et al.*, 2017), and Georgia (Cholokava, 1996, 2008; Gogoberidze, 2006).

Biology. Mesophilic, nocturnal species inhabiting deciduous and mixed forests (Yunakov, 2003 b; Yunakov *et al.*, 2018 a). The species is a dendrobiotic and polyphagous, feeds on *Acer tataricum*, *Carpinus* sp., *Crataegus* sp., *Fagus* sp., *Malus pumila*, *Quercus* sp., *Pyrus eleagrifolia*,

Figs 1–2. Maps of *Otiorhynchus* distribution: 1 — *O. balcanicus* in Ukraine; 2 — *O. pilosus pilosus* in the Palearctic Region. Insufficient data — records with no date and/or coordinates with low precision.

Rosa sp., *Sambucus nigra*, and *Ulmus* sp. (Yunakov, 2003 b; Poiras, 2006; Yunakov *et al.*, 2018 a). The species could damage *Acca sellowiana*, *Citrus limon*, *C. reticulata*, *C. sinensis*, *Laurus nobilis*, *M. pumila*, *Prunus persica*, *Pyrus communis*, *Ribes rubrum*, *Rosa* sp., *Rubus* sp., and other plants in Georgia (Cholokava, 1996), and grapes in Eastern Caucasus (Abdullagatova, 2009). Ukrainian populations of the species are parthenogenetic whereas the bisexual form is represented in Western Caucasus (Yunakov, 2003 b; Yunakov *et al.*, 2018 a). It may suggest that the species originates from this region.

Taxonomic notes. Some researchers suggest that *O. pilosus* should be excluded from the subgenus *Choilisanus* (Davidian & Keskin, 2010; Davidian & Gültekin, 2015). Except for the nominative subspecies, *O. pilosus samsunensis* Smreczynski, 1977 has been described from Turkey (Alonso-Zarazaga *et al.*, 2017).

Otiorhynchus (Choilisanus) raucus (Fabricius, 1777)

Material examined. **Cherkasy Region:** Kaniv Nature Reserve, 49.723254°N 31.535330°E, 10–13.06.2011, 1 ♀ (Kizub); **Chernihiv Region:** Ichnia, 50.84503°N 32.34780°E, 25–27.06.2004, 1 ♀ (Kizub); idem, 21–26.08.2011, 2 ♀ (Kizub); idem, 29.04–01.05.2012, 2 ♀ (Kizub); **Kyiv Region:** Bilohorodka, 50.364814°N 30.220398°E, 26.07.2009, 1 ♀ (Kizub); Sofiivska Borshchahivka, 50.41424°N 30.36681°E, 10.04.2005, 2 ♀ (Kizub); Kyiv, Shuliavka, 50.45727°N 30.44048°E, 06.10.2008, 1 ♀ (Kizub); idem, 26.06.2010, 2 ♀ (Kizub); idem, 01–02.06.2011, 1 ♀ (Kizub); Kyiv, Voskresenka, City Clinic Hospital № 3 area, 50.477584°N 30.603616°E, 08–11.06.2010, 1 ♀ (Kizub); Kyiv, Golosiivo, 50.381091°N 30.520870°E, 03.04.2011, 1 ♀ (Kizub).

Distribution. Almost whole territory of Ukraine except of Kherson, Luhansk, Mykolaiv, Odesa, and Poltava Regions (Yunakov, 2003 b; Yunakov *et al.*, 2018 a). Whole Europe, Georgia, Kazakhstan, and West Siberia (Alonso-Zarazaga *et al.*, 2017). Introduced in Azores Islands (Alonso-Zarazaga *et al.*, 2017), Canada (Warner & Negley, 1976; McNamara, 1991), and the USA (O'Brien & Wibmer, 1982).

Biology. The species is mesophylic, polyphagous and inhabits in deciduous forests (Yunakov, 2003 b; Yunakov *et al.*, 2018 a). Phyllophagous, feeds on plants of genera *Betula*, *Acer*, *Rosa*, *Crataegus*, *Rubus*, *Geum*, *Fragaria*, *Spiraea*, *Artemisia*, and *Mattheuccia* (Yunakov, 2003 b). It has been reported that the beetle could damage leaves of *Brassica rapa*, *Beta vulgaris*, and *Rheum* sp., buds and shoots of *Malus* sp., *Pyrus* sp., *Prunus* sp., *Vitis* sp., *Rubus* sp., *Saxifraga* sp., and *Olea europaea* (Stackelberg, 1932). The Ukrainian population of the species is parthenogenetic (Yunakov *et al.*, 2018). The bisexual population of *O. raucus* has been discovered in the Southern Balkan and lies at the southern border of the species range (Mazur, 2003). It may suggest that the species originates from the Balkan Peninsula (Mazur, 2003).

Otiorhynchus (Choilisanus) velutinus Germar, 1824

Material examined. **Crimea:** Kerch, Mitridat Mt., 45.35053°N 36.46958°E, 12–20.04.1999, 1 ♀ (collector unknown).

Distribution. Ukraine: Crimea, Chernihiv, Cherkasy, Donetsk, Ivano-Frankivsk, Kherson, Kharkiv, Kyiv, Luhansk, Lviv, Mykolaiv, Odesa, Poltava, Ternopil, Volyn, and Zakarpatska Regions (Mazur, 2002; Yunakov *et al.*, 2018 a). Almost whole Europe, Southwestern and Central Asia, and West Siberia (Alonso-Zarazaga *et al.*, 2017).

Biology. Parthenogenetic, nocturnal, meso-xerothermic species inhabiting steppes and xerothermic grasslands (Mazur, 2002; Yunakov *et al.*, 2018). *Otiorhynchus velutinus* is a polyphagous and chortobiotic species feeding mainly on plants of the order Rosales, families Asteraceae and Poaceae including *Salvia* sp., *Fragaria* sp., and *Elymus repens* (Yunakov, 2003 b).

Otiorhynchus (Cryphiphorus) ligustici (Linnaeus, 1758)

Material examined. **Crimea:** Saky District, Trudove, 45.236028°N 33.756827°E, 10.05.2010, 1 ♀ (Khalin); Bakhchisarai District, Malyi Babulgan Hole, h = 1000 m, 44.48582°N 33.958144°E, 04.05.2009, 1 ♀ (Kizub); **Kyiv Region:** Sofiivska Borshchahivka, 50.41424°N 30.36681°E, 03.05.2004, 1 ♀ (Kizub); idem, 04.06.2005, 1 ♀ (Kizub); idem, 25.06.2005, 1 ♀ (Kizub); Kyiv, Pechersk, 50.42387°N 30.54062°E, 07.05.2000, 1 ♀ (Kizub); **Lviv Region:** Skole District, Slavske env., Trostian Mt., h = 700–1230 m, 48.85350°N, 23.38614°E, 02–04.06.2012, 3 ♀ (Kizub); **Zakarpatska Region:** Uzhgorod District, Stuzhytsya env., 49.01637°N 22.58898°E, 16.06.2009, 1 ♀ (Kurennyi).

Distribution. Ukraine: All regions without exception (Yunakov *et al.*, 2018). Whole Europe, Southwestern Asia, Kazakhstan, and West Siberia (Alonso-Zarazaga *et al.*, 2017). The species introduced in Canada (McNamara, 1991) and the USA (Warner & Negley, 1976; O'Brien & Wibmer, 1982).

Biology. *Otiorhynchus ligustici* is a polytopic, meso-xerothermic species inhabiting steppes, bushlands, floodplain meadows and meadows in forests (Yunakov, 2003 b; Yunakov *et al.*, 2018). Polyphagous chortobiotic species that feeds mainly on *Achillea* sp., *Fallopia convolvulus*, *Genista tinctoria*, *Heracleum* sp., *Ligusticum* sp., *Lithrum* sp., *Medicago* sp., *Melilotus officinalis*, *Polygonum aviculare*, *Rumex* sp., *Salvia verticillata*, *Trifolium* sp., *Urtica dioica*, *Vicia* sp., and *Xanthium spinosum* (Stackelberg, 1932; Yunakov, 2003 b). The species has been indicated as a pest of *Asparagus* sp., *Beta vulgaris*, *Corylus avellana*, *Fragaria* sp., *Helianthus annuus*, *Humulus lupulus*, *Lupinus* sp., *Medicago sativa*, *M. officinalis*, *Onobrychis* sp., *Papaver somniferum*, *Phaseolus vulgaris*, *Pisum sativum*, *Rosa cinnamomea*, *Solanum melongena*, *Trifolium* sp., *Vicia faba*, *Vitis* sp., and fruit trees (Stackelberg, 1932; Yunakov, 2003 b; Abdullagatova, 2009). Larvae damage underground parts of plants (Stackelberg, 1932; Yunakov, 2003 b). The Ukrainian populations of the species are parthenogenetic (Yunakov *et al.*, 2018 a), and the bisexual population of *O. ligustici* is known mainly from the Balkan Peninsula and a few males have been found in Ukraine (Yunakov, 2003 b; Yunakov *et al.*, 2018 a).

***Otiorhynchus (Duphanastus) aurosparsus* Germar, 1824 (Fig. 3)**

Material examined. Chernihiv Region: Ichnya, 50.84503°N 32.34780°E, 12.06.2000, 1 ♀ (Kizub).

Distribution. Ukraine: Donetsk, Kharkiv (Yunakov, 2003 b; Yunakov *et al.*, 2018 a), and Chernihiv Regions. This is the first record of *O. aurosparsus* in Chernihiv Region of Ukraine and so far the northernmost record of this species in the territory of Ukraine. Occurrence of *O. aurosparsus* in the Crimea (Yunakov, 2003 b; Yunakov *et al.*, 2018 a) probably needs confirmation. Russian Rostov Region (Poltavskiy & Arzanov, 1998; Minoranskiy *et al.*, 2002; Arzanov, 2015), Stavropol Krai (Uvarov & Glazunov, 1916; Arzanov, 2001; Arzanov, 2012; Szymroszczyk, 2018), Krasnodar Krai (Korotyaev & Zabaluev, 2014), the Kabardino-Balkar Republic (Bolov & Bolov, 1997), the Republic of Adygea (Korotyaev & Arzanov, 2010; Zamotajlov, 2012; Korotyaev & Zabaluev, 2014), Ukraine (Yunakov, 2003b; Yunakov *et al.*, 2018), Armenia, and Georgia (Alonso-Zarazaga *et al.*, 2017).

listed in the Revisited Checklist of the weevils of Poland (Wanat & Mokrzycki, 2018). Despite the species has been included in the Catalogue of the Weevils of the Republic of Moldova (Poiras, 1998), the Checklist of beetles of the Republic of Moldova (Bacal *et al.*, 2013), and listed for Moldova in CCPCC (Alonso-Zarazaga *et al.*, 2017), its occurrence in the territory of this country is doubtful (Poiras, 2006). The species has also been mentioned for the Latvian and Estonian fauna in CCPCC (Alonso-Zarazaga *et al.*, 2017), however, it is also doubtful whether it ever occurred in the territory of these countries (Telnov, 2004). Findings of this species in Russian Voronezh (Negrobov *et al.*, 2005) and Saratov Regions needs confirmation as well (Zabaluev, 2016).

Otiorhynchus aurosparsus has been included in The Red Lists of Russian Rostov Region and the Republic of Adygea as a rare and poorly investigated species (Minoranskiy *et al.*, 2002; Zamotajlov, 2012), and has been recommended to The Red List of Moldova as a species with indeterminate status of the rarity (Poiras, 2006). The species is also very rare in Ukraine and so far is known from

Fig. 3 Map of *Otiorhynchus aurosparsus* distribution in the Palearctic Region. Insufficient data — records with no date and/or coordinates with low precision.

The species has been included in the Catalog of beetles of Belarus (Alexandrovitch *et al.*, 1996), however, it is known from the Polish part of the Białowieża Primeval Forest (Belovezhskaya Pushcha), and documented records of this species in Belarus are absent (Sautkin & Meleshko, 2016). On the other hand, the species has not also been

few localities (see Fig. 4). In our opinion, *O. aurosparsus* should be included in The Red Lists of Chernihiv Region of Ukraine and The Red Lists of Ukraine as a rare species on the border of its range.

Biology. Parthenogenetic, nocturnal, mesophylic species inhabiting deciduous forests, bushlands, and wood-

and-steppes (Yunakov, 2003 b; Poiras, 2006; Yunakov *et al.*, 2018 a). Polyphagous, dedrobiotic, phillophagous species feeding on *Carpinus betulus* and other arboreal and shrubby vegetation (Yunakov, 2003 b). We have found this species feeding on *Urtica dioica* in the Kabardino-Balkar Republic of Russia. From the Caucasus *O. aurosparsus* has been reported as a pest damaging buds and leaves of *Cydonia oblonga*, *Malus pumila*, *Pyrus communis*, *Prunus cerasus*, *P. avium*, *P. padus*, *P. armeniaca*, *Ribes nigrum*, *R. uva-crispa*, *Rubus idaeus*, and *Vitis* sp. (Stackelberg, 1932; Yunakov, 2003 b; Poiras, 2006).

***Otiorynchus (Melasemnus) ovalipennis* Boheman, 1842**

Material examined. **Crimea:** Sevastopol, Blakytina Bay, 44.55621°N 33.40852°E, 04.08.2004, 3 ♀ (Tkachenko); Sevastopol, Kozacha Bay, 44.583501°N 33.415021°E, 6–19.07.2006, 5 ♀ (Kizub); idem, 07–17.08.2013, 1 ♀ (Kizub); idem, 18–21.08.2013, 1 ♀ (Kharchenko); Bakhchysarai District, Mangup-Kale, 44.59281°N 33.80604°E, 01.05.2009, 1 ♀ (Kizub).

Distribution. Ukraine: the Crimea, Odesa Region, introduced in Kyiv and Lviv Regions (Yunakov, 2003 b; Yunakov *et al.*, 2018 a, b). Southern and Eastern Europe, Southwestern Asia, and Middle East (Alonso-Zarazaga *et al.*, 2017).

Biology. Nocturnal, parthenogenetic species inhabiting mountain meso-xerothermic forests (Yunakov, 2003 b; Yunakov *et al.*, 2018). Dendrobiotic phyllophagous species feeding on various plants including *Artemisia* sp., *Carpinus orientalis*, *Crataegus* sp., *Cerasus microcarpa*, *Cornus mas*, *Cupressus sempervirens*, *Eriobotrya japonica*, *Juniperus excelsa*, *Ligustrum vulgare*, *Morus alba*, *Olea europaea*, *Prunus dulcis*, *P. cerasus*, *P. domestica*, *P. persica*, *Qercus petraea*, *Q. pubescens*, *Rosa* sp., *Rubus* sp., and *Sorbus taurica* (Yunakov, 2003 b; Özbek, 2016; Yunakov *et al.*, 2018 a). It has been reported that beetles could damage leaves of *P. cerasus* (Özbek, 2016) and other fruit trees, and grapes (Yunakov, 2003 b).

***Otiorynchus (Namertanus) pseudomias* Hochhuth, 1847**

Material examined. **Crimea:** Bakhchisarai District, Demerdjy Yaila, Pakkal-Kaja Mt., h = 1000 m., 44.76666° N 34.41666° E, 25–26.07.2011, 1 ♀ (Kizub).

Distribution. Ukraine: Crimea (Yunakov, 2003 b; Yunakov *et al.*, 2018 a, b). Bosnia and Herzegovina, Croatia, Slovenia, southern European territory of Russia, Ukraine, Armenia, Azerbaijan, Georgia, and the Northeastern Turkey (Davidian & Savitsky, 2006).

Biology. Parthenogenetic, mesophilic geobiotic species inhabiting mountain deciduous forests in leaf litter and under stones (Yunakov, 2003 b; Davidian & Savitsky, 2006; Yunakov *et al.*, 2018 a). The species is a polyphagous, dendrito-phylophagous feeding on rotting

plant remains, living parts of herbaceous plants and mushrooms (Yunakov, 2003 b; Yunakov *et al.*, 2018 a).

***Otiorynchus (Otirolehus) tristis* (Scopoli, 1763)**

Material examined. **Chernihiv Region:** Ichnia, 50.84503°N 32.34780°E, 07.2000, 1 ♀ (Kizub); idem, 25–27.06.2004, 1 ♀ (Kizub); **Kyiv Region:** Kyiv, Novobilychi, 50.47912°N 30.32640°E, 10.06.2006, 1 ♀ (Kizub); **Zhytomyr Region:** Dovzhyk env., 50.30784°N 28.57440°E, 06.06.2009, 1 ♀ (Kurennyi).

Distribution. Ukraine: Chernihiv, Cherkasy, Donetsk, Kharkiv, Kyiv, Sumy, Vinnytsia, Volyn, Zakarpatska, and Zhytomyr Regions (Yunakov *et al.*, 2018 a, b). Most part of Europe, Central Asia, and Siberia (Alonso-Zarazaga *et al.*, 2017).

Biology. Xero-mesophilic species inhabiting steppes and scattered bushlands (Yunakov, 2003 b; Yunakov *et al.*, 2018 a). In Ukraine the species is represented by parthenogenetic populations whereas bisexual populations are known from Moldova and the Balkan Peninsula (Yunakov, 2003 b; Yunakov *et al.*, 2018 a). Polyphagous, dendro-tamno-chortobiotic species feeding mainly on *Artemisia vulgare*, *Crataegus* sp., *Quercus* sp., *Sorbus* sp., *Rubus* sp., *Rumex acerosa*, *Salvia* sp., *Tanacetum vulgare*, *Ulmus* sp., and *Urtica dioica* (Yunakov, 2003 b). May damage lives of *Salvia officinalis* (Yunakov, 2003 b).

***Otiorynchus (Pendragon) ovatus ovatus* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Material examined. **Chernihiv Region:** Ichnia, 50.84503°N 32.34780°E, 08.2003, 1 ♀ (Kizub); idem, 21–26.08.2011, 2 ♀ (Kizub); **Chernivtsi Region:** Kutu — Kniazhe, Cheremosh river bank, 48.35025°N 25.29476°E, 02.05.2006, 1 ♀ (Kizub). **Kyiv Region:** Kyiv, city centre, 50.44036 30.52958, 09.04.2005, 1 ♀ (Kizub); Kyiv, Shuliavka, 50.45727°N 30.44048°E, 06.10.2008, 1 ♀ (Kizub); idem, 20.05.2009, 1 ♀ (Kizub); idem, 02–04.06.2015, 1 ♀ (Kizub); Sofiivska Borshchahivka, 50.41424°N 30.36681°E, 24.04.2005, 1 ♀ (Kizub); idem, 25.06.2005, 1 ♀ (Kizub); Nova Buda, Spartak railway station environs, 50.68001°N 29.72647°E, 24.04.2010, 1 ♀ (Kizub).

Distribution. Almost whole territory of Ukraine except of Kherson and Mykolaiv Regions (Yunakov, 2003 b; Yunakov *et al.*, 2018 a). Almost whole Europe, Azerbaijan, Central Asia, and Siberia (Alonso-Zarazaga *et al.*, 2017). Introduced in Canada (Warner & Negley, 1976; McNamara, 1991; Webster, 2016), the USA (Warner & Negley, 1976; O'Brien & Wibmer, 1982), and New Zealand (Yunakov *et al.*, 2018 a).

Biology. Polytopic, mesophylic, parthenogenetic species (Yunakov, 2003 b; Yunakov *et al.*, 2018 a). Polyphagous, chortobiotic species feeding mainly on plants of the family *Rosacea* (Yunakov, 2003 b; Yunakov *et al.*, 2018 a) and has been recorded on *Salix* sp., *Rosa* sp., *Fragaria vesca*, and *Sonchus arvensis* (Yunakov *et al.*, 2018 b). *Otiorynchus ovatus* could damage fruit

and coniferous trees, grapes, *Fragaria* sp., and *Rubus* sp. (Yunakov, 2003 b; Abdullagatova, 2009; Yunakov *et al.*, 2018 a).

Taxonomic notes. Except for the nominative one, the subspecies *glacialis* Apfelbeck, 1898 has been described from the Balkan Peninsula (Alonso-Zarazaga *et al.*, 2017).

***Otiorhynchus* (*Pocodalemes*) *vitis theodosianus* Retowski, 1887 (Figs 4–5)**

Material examined. Crimea: Sevastopol, Kozacha Bay, 44.583501°N 33.415021°E, 03.08.2004, 2 ex. (Kizub); idem 6–19.07.2006, 6 ex. (Kizub).

Distribution. The species is endemic to Ukraine: the Crimea and Kherson Region (Yunakov, 1998, 2003 b; Yunakov *et al.*, 2018 a) (Fig. 5).

Biology. Xerophilic species inhabiting steps and solonetz soils on the plain and in the foothills (Yunakov, 2003 b; Yunakov *et al.*, 2018 a). Polyphagous and chortobiotic species feeding mostly on *Artemisia* sp. (Yunakov, 2003 b; Yunakov *et al.*, 2018 a).

Taxonomic notes. Some authors refer *O. vitis* Gyllenhal, 1834 to the subgenus *Panorosemus* (Vit *et al.*, 2018; Yunakov *et al.*, 2018 a). The nominative subspecies is an endemic to the Mountain Crimea (Yunakov, 2003 b; Yunakov *et al.*, 2018 a).

Figs 4–5. *Otiorhynchus vitis theodosianus*: 4 — habitus, dorsally, Crimea, Sevastopol, Kozacha Bay. Scale bar = 1 mm; 5 — distribution in Ukraine. Insufficient data — records with no date and/or coordinates with low precision.

***Otiorhynchus (Podoropelmus) albidus* Stierlin, 1861 (Fig. 6)**

Material examined. Crimea: Sevastopol, Kozacha Bay, 44.583501°N 33.415021°E, 6–19.07.2006, 5 ♀ (Kizub); Saki District, Trudove, 45.236028°N 33.756827°E, 22–29.07.2009, 1 ♀ (Khalin).

Distribution. Ukraine: the Crimea, Kherson, Kropyvnytskyi, Odesa, and Zaporizhia Regions (Magnano, 1999; Yunakov *et al.*, 2018 a). Southern and Eastern Europe (Alonso-Zarazaga *et al.*, 2017). Introduced in Austria (Schuh *et al.*, 2015; Yunakov *et al.*, 2018 a), Germany (Yunakov *et al.*, 2018 a), North of European part of Russia (Korotyaev *et al.*, 2018), and Southeastern Kazakhstan (Kolov and Korotyaev, 2017). In the Republic of Moldova the species is treated as an invader (Munteanu *et al.*, 2014).

Biology. The species lives in sub-mountain and lowland xerothermic bushlands, semidry broadleaf and Mediterranean forests (Yunakov *et al.*, 2018 a). Ukrainian populations of the species are parthenogenetic (Yunakov, 2003 b; Yunakov *et al.*, 2018 a). The bisexual form is represented in the Greece and one male, described as *O. strictipennis* Magnano, 1999, has been found in the Crimea (Magnano, 1999; Yunakov, 2003 b; Yunakov *et al.*, 2018 a). Beetles are nocturnal, dendrobiotic and polyphagous feeding on *Carpinus orientalis*, *Clematis* sp., *Cornus mas*, *Crataegus* sp., *Juglans* sp., *Prunus spinosa*, *Quercus pubescens*, *Q. petraea*, *Rosa* sp., *Ulmus* sp. (Yunakov, 2003 b), *Populus* sp., *Tamarix* sp., *Tilia* sp. (Munteanu *et al.*, 2014), *Pinus sylvestris*, *Prunus cerasus*, and *Syringa vulgaris* (Kolov and Korotyaev, 2017; Korotyaev *et al.*, 2018). The species has been reported as a pest of fruit trees and *Crataegus* sp. (Arnoldi *et al.*, 1974).

***Otiorhynchus (Podoropelmus) fullo* (Schrank, 1781)**

Material examined. Donetsk Region: Donetsk, Botanical Garden, 48.003297°N 37.891087°E, 26.05.2010, 1 ♀ (collector unknown); Kharkiv Region: Dokuchaievsk env., 49.888475°N 36.455356°E, 07–13.06.2005, 5 ♀ (Shekhovtsov); Kharkiv, Shevchenkivskiy [Dzerzhinsky] District, 50.059635°N 36.232710°E, 18–21.05.2009, 3 ♀ (Shekhovtsov); idem, 25.05.2009, 9 ♀ (Shekhovtsov & Loboda); Kyiv Region: Kyiv, Golosiivo, 50.381091°N 30.520870°E, 09.06.1994, 4 ♀ (Kravchenko); Odesa Region: Balta District, Lisnychivka env., 48.019659°N 29.540097°E, 18.06.2012, 2 ♀ (Kravchenko).

Distribution. Almost whole territory of Ukraine except of Dnipro, Kherson, Poltava, Sumy, and Zaporizhia Regions (Yunakov *et al.*, 2018 a). Central, Southeastern, and Eastern Europe, Kazakhstan, and West Siberia (Alonso-Zarazaga *et al.*, 2017).

Biology. Nocturnal, xero-mesophylic, dendro-tamno-chortobitic species inhabiting xerothermic bushlands, mixed forests, and fruit plantations (Yunakov *et al.*, 2018 a). The Ukrainian populations of the species are parthenogenetic, bisexual form of *O. fullo* is known from the Balkan Peninsula (Yunakov *et al.*, 2018 a). Polyphagous, phillophagous species feeding on *Acer platanoides*, *Armeniaca* sp., *Crataegus* sp., *Betula* sp., *Malus* sp., *Quercus robur*, *Sorbus* sp., *Spirea* sp., *Prunus* sp., *Pyracantha coccinea*, *Pyrus* sp., *Rosa canina*, *Rubus*

sp., *Ulmus* sp., *Veronica* sp. (Yunakov, 2003 b). It has been reported that beetles could damage fruit trees, grapes, *Rubus idaeus*, and *Rosa* sp. (Arnoldi *et al.*, 1974; Yunakov, 2003 b).

***Otiorhynchus (Pontotiorhynchus) asphaltinus* Germar, 1824 (Fig. 7)**

=*creticola* Arnoldi, 1964

Material examined. Crimea: Sevastopol, National Preserve of Tauric Chersonesos, 44.612311°N 33.491855°E, 24.07.2004, 2 ♂ (Kizub); Kyiv Region: Kyiv, Shuliavka, 50.45986652°N 30.43650722°E, 13.07.2015, 1 ♀ (Kizub); idem, 19.09.2017, 1 ♀ (Kizub); idem, 26.10.2017, 1 ♀ (Kizub).

Distribution. Ukraine: Crimea, Donetsk, Kherson, Kharkiv, and Luhansk Regions (Yunakov, 2003 b; Nazarenko & Sheshurak, 2003; Yunakov & Drovalenko, 2013; Yunakov *et al.*, 2018 a). Introduced in Kyiv Region (Yunakov *et al.*, 2018 a). Europe: Moldova (Yunakov, 2003 a), central and southern European part of Russia (Yunakov, 2003 a; Shkuratov, 2004; Prisyazhnyuk, 2004; Tsupikov, 2009; Komarov, 2010; Negrobov, 2011; Panteleeva & Sobolev, 2012; Korotyaev & Zabaluev, 2014; Arzanov, 2015; Batishcheva & Negrobov, 2017; Brekhov, 2018), and Ukraine (Yunakov *et al.*, 2018 a). Introduced in North of European Russia (St.-Petersburg) (Korotyaev *et al.*, 2018).

Otiorhynchus asphaltinus has been included in The Red List of Kharkiv Region of Ukraine as a rare species on the border of its range (Yunakov and Drovalenko, 2013) and has also been listed in The Red Lists of Belgorod, Lipetsk, and Voronezh Regions of Russia (Prisyazhnyuk, 2004; Tsupikov, 2009; Negrobov, 2011).

Biology. Nocturnal, xero-mesophylic, tamno-chortobitic species inhabiting mountain deciduous and Mediterranean forests, as well as bushlands on limestone and chalk in the wood-and-steppe and steppe (Yunakov, 2003 a, b; Yunakov *et al.*, 2018 a). Polyphagous species feeding on *Acer tataricum*, *Alchemilla* sp., *Betula* sp., *Crataegus* sp., *Fragaria* sp., *Juniperus sabina*, *M. pumila*, *Potentilla* sp., *Prunus avium*, *P. dulcis*, *P. elaeagrifolia*, *Rosa* sp., *Sorbus aucuparia*, *Syringa josikaea*, *S. vulgaris*, and *Ulmus* sp. (Yunakov, 2003 a, b; Dudnyk, 2011; Korotyaev *et al.*, 2018; Yunakov *et al.*, 2018 a). The species could damage fruit trees and *Crataegus* sp. in the Crimea (Yunakov, 2003 b) and by mistake for a long time was treated as a serious pest of vineyards (Yunakov, 2003 a, b; Dudnyk, 2011; Yunakov & Drovalenko, 2013).

***Otiorhynchus (Pontotiorhynchus) atronitens* Formánek, 1925**

Material examined. Crimea: Sevastopol, National Preserve of Tauric Chersonesos, 44.61231°N 33.49185°E, 24.07.2004, 1 ♀ (Kizub); Yalta District, Nikita, 44.513692°N 34.23896°E, 28.09.2004, 1 ♀ (Kizub); Bakchysarai District, Chufut-Kale, 44.740862°N 33.922858°E, 17.08.2006, 1 ♀ (Tkachenko); Saky District, Trudove, 45.236028°N 33.756827°E, 21–23.07.2011, 1 ♀ (Khalin); Sevastopol, Kozacha Bay, 44.583501°N 33.415021°E, 07–17.08.2013, 1 ♀ (Kizub).

Figs 6–7. Maps of *Otiorhynchus* distribution: 6 — *O. albidus* in Ukraine; 7 — *O. asphaltinus* in the Palearctic Region. Insufficient data — records with no date and/or coordinates with low precision.

Distribution. Ukraine: the Crimea (Yunakov, 2003 a, b; Yunakov *et al.*, 2018 a, b). *Otiorhynchus atronitens* is known from Krasnodar Krai of Russia and Ukraine only (Yunakov, 2003 a, b; Yunakov *et al.*, 2018 a) and is the Orocrimean subendemic species.

Biology. *Otiorhynchus atronitens* is a nocturnal, meso-xerophytic, tamno-chortobiotic species inhabiting mountain and lowland mixed, and Mediterranean forests, shrublands, and mountain grasslands (Yunakov, 2003 a, b; Yunakov *et al.*, 2018 a). Polyphagous on arboreal and shrubby vegetation, mainly *Cotinus* sp., *Crataegus* sp., *Juniperus* sp., *Prunus* sp., *Rosa* sp. (Yunakov, 2003 a, b).

Otiorhynchus (Pontotiorhynchus) brauneri Smirnov, 1910

Material examined. Crimea: Sevastopol, Kozacha Bay, 44.583501°N 33.415021°E, 6–19.07.2006, 2 ♂ (Kizub); Bakhchysarai District, Malyi Babulgan Hole — Besh-Tekne, h = 1000 m, 44.48582°N 33.95814°E, 04.05.2009, 2 ♂, 1 ♀ (Kizub); Bakhchysarai District, Kuru-Mezen River, Besh-Dere, h = 700 m, 44.47799°N, 34.10258°E, 01.05.2010, 2 ♂, 6 ♀ (Kizub); Bakhchysarai District, Sary-Uzen, Silver Streams [Sribni Strumeni] Waterfall, h = 600 m, 44.51656°N, 33.97692°E, 01–02.05.2010, 1 ♀ (Kizub).

Distribution. Ukraine: Endemic to the Crimea (Yunakov, 2003 a, b; Yunakov *et al.*, 2018 a, b).

Biology. Nocturnal, xero-mesophytic, chortobiotic species inhabiting Mediterranean shrublands and mountain grasslands. Polyphagous, phillophagous species feeding on herbaceous plants and shrubs (Yunakov, 2003 b; Yunakov *et al.*, 2018 a).

Conclusions

Of the 17 species of the genus *Otiorhynchus* reported in the present paper, *O. raucus*, *O. velutinus*, *O. ligustici*, *O. tristis*, *O. ovatus ovatus*, and *O. fullo* are widely distributed in the Western Palearctic Region and Ukraine. A few species has Alpino-Caucasian-Eastern Mediterranean-Irano-Turanian (*O. balcanicus*, *O. ovalipennis*), Alpino-Caucasian-Eastern Mediterranean (*O. albidus*), Ilyrio-Euxino-Caucasian (*O. pseudomias*), and Eastern Alpino-Caucasian (*O. pilosus pilosus*) ranges. The northern border of ranges of some species passes through the southeastern (*O. brunneus*, *O. pilosus pilosus*) or southern (*O. albidus*, *O. ovalipennis*) districts of Ukraine. A few species discussed here are Orocrimean subendemic (*O. atronitens*), endemic to the Crimea (*O. brauneri*), or endemic to the south of Ukraine and a rare (*O. vitis theodosianus*).

Otiorhynchus brunneus, *O. ovalipennis*, and *O. asphaltinus* have been introduced into Kyiv Region. In this paper we report new evidences of *O. asphaltinus* introducing into Kyiv Region. The species is quite rare in the northeastern part of its natural range, including Eastern Ukraine.

Also, in the present paper we report the northernmost record of *O. aurosparsus* in Ukraine and the first record of this species in Chernihiv Region of Ukraine. The data

presented suggest that *O. aurosparsus* has a Central Russian-Escitio-Caucasian range and is very rare in Ukraine and a few other parts of its range. In our opinion the species should be included in The Red Lists of Ukraine and The Red Lists of Chernihiv Region of Ukraine as a rare species on the border of its range.

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